

Low-Cost Hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS Integration for Seamless Indoor/Outdoor UAV Navigation

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BIOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) performance may be seriously degraded under harsh propagation conditions, or totally denied indoors. In such scenarios, to provide precise, accurate and reliable navigation information, GNSS must be combined with other sources of information. In this contribution, we leverage on the use of Ultra-WideBand (UWB) based distance measurements and Inertial Navigation Systems (INS), and provide a hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS sensor fusion strategy for robust seamless indoor/outdoor unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) navigation. Results are provided for a real UAV scenario.

1. INTRODUCTION

GNSS is the technology of choice for positioning outdoors. Such systems provide good positioning capabilities under nominal conditions, but their performance may be severely degraded under harsh propagation conditions, such as dense multipath or non-line-of-sight (NLOS) conditions, being typically the case in urban canyons. Then, to obtain reliable positioning, GNSS have to be combined with other sources of information. Moreover, GNSS may not available indoors (or in other GNSS-denied environments), thus other means of positioning have to be accounted for in such scenarios.

Several technologies exist to obtain alternative positioning solutions: WiFi-based positioning from received signal strength (RSS) measurements is easy to use due to the already deployed infrastructure, but the performance is typically in the order of some meters, which may not be enough in safety-critical applications and/or indoor environments; INS are self-contained but have inherent sensor noises and measurement biases. In the case of low-cost INS, this prevents its use as a standalone navigation system, and the size and weight of high-end INS do not allow to use them in small unmanned vehicles such as drones; the use of LTE/5G-based positioning requires communication capabilities; Impulse-Radio Ultra-WideBand (IR-UWB) requires a dedicated infrastructure, but provides subdecimeter-level precision. Overall, each technology has its own pros and cons, and therefore a robust seamless navigation solution must consider multi-sensor data fusion strategies, using two or more of these alternatives.

Typically, legacy multi-sensor architectures (i.e., GNSS/INS fusion) are classified depending of its level of integration [1]: i) loose integration if both GNSS/INS are combined at the position/velocity level, ii) tight integration if GNSS pseudorange and pseudorange rate measurements are combined with INS position and velocity, and iii) ultra-tight integration if the fusion is done at the GNSS tracking level. Low-cost GNSS typically only allow to access the position, velocity, timing (PVT) solution and not the corresponding observables or direct access to the synchronization stage, then the loose GNSS/INS is the only option.

Due to advances in sensor processing and battery technologies over the past decade, Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UASs) have become both smaller and more affordable [2]. In the near future, the airspace is expected to be populated with a large number of unmanned as well as manned aircrafts, a majority of which are expected to be operating autonomously. For this reason, precise localization is one of the key requirements in the deployment of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for a plethora of applications [3]. The goal of this contribution is to provide a low-cost hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS data fusion architecture, where INS position/velocity are combined with GNSS PVT and cooperative UWB-based distance measurements, for seamless indoor/outdoor UAV navigation. The use of UWB allows to obtain high precision when needed, that is, indoors and/or in safety-critical areas, and rely on the standard GNSS/INS in clear-sky areas or where the precision system requirements are lower (i.e., limiting the indiscriminate deployment of additional infrastructure).

A prototype has been developed (using the MDEK1001 kit by Decawave to obtain UWB-based distance measurements), and results for a real indoor/outdoor UAV navigation scenario are provided to show the promising performances of such approach. Considering that the corresponding UWB infrastructure can be deployed, the hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS presented in this article is not only a powerful solution for autonomous UAV navigation in warehouses, factories or smart cities, but also for driverless cars and vulnerable road users (pedestrians, bicycles).

2. MULTI-SENSOR DATA FUSION

Several alternatives have been studied in the literature to improve real-time positioning for different types of vehicles, including UAVs. A common approach is to use multi-sensor data fusion strategies, that is, different systems which provide position-related information are combined to obtain improved performance. Depending on the nature of the information used within the fusion, different architectures are distinguished [1], mainly loose, tight and ultra-tight integration. When using low-cost sensors, the standard approaches may not be reliable enough, and then several improvements can be accounted for [4].

Standard sensor integration strategies consider GNSS/INS data fusion, which do not provide the required system performance under harsh propagation conditions, in GNSS-denied environments, or for safety-critical applications, then other sensors must be used to improve the overall system performance. In this contribution, as already stated, we consider the use of IR-UWB sensors, which are known to be robust to multipath and NLOS effects, and can achieve subdecimeter-level ranging errors. It is out of the scope to provide a state-of-the-art on multi-sensor data fusion, but we acknowledge a related work in [5], where the proposed solution was only tested in a simulated scenario.

Because the core of the hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS fusion is the strapdown INS, in the sequel the INS mathematical background is provided, followed by the state-space model (SSM) for both loose and hybrid fusion solutions.

2.1. Strapdown Inertial Navigation System (INS)

The strapdown (i.e., inertial sensors attached to the body) equations are used to obtain attitude, velocity and position at the output of the INS. The input to the INS are acceleration (forces) and angular velocity¹, $\mathbf{f}_{ib,t}^b$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b$, in the body frame; the time interval between inertial measurement unit (IMU) measurement epochs (s) is τ_i , the earth rotation rate (rad/s) is $\omega_{ie} = 7.292115e^{-5}$, and $\alpha_{ie,t} = \omega_{ie}\tau_i$. The attitude increment, magnitude, skew-symmetric matrix of the IMU's angular-rate measurement, Earth-rotation vector and associated skew-symmetric matrix, are given by

$$\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{ib,t}^b \approx \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b \tau_i \text{ (constant angular rate over } \tau_i), \quad m_{\alpha,t} = (\boldsymbol{\alpha}_{ib,t}^b)^T \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{ib,t}^b,$$

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ib,t}^b = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b(3) & \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b(2) \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b(3) & 0 & -\boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b(1) \\ -\boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b(2) & \boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b(1) & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \boldsymbol{\alpha}_{ie} = [0, 0, \alpha_{ie}]^T, \quad \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ie}^e = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\omega_{ie} & 0 \\ \omega_{ie} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

From these accelerations and angular velocities, the outputs of the INS are computed as follows:

- Attitude (Coordinate Transformation matrix and Euler Angles) - $\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^e$ and $\boldsymbol{\psi}_{b,t}^e$

The Euler angles are obtained from the coordinate transformation matrix, $\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^e$, which is directly related to the angular velocities given by the IMU, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b$. First, the coordinate transformation matrix is updated from $t-1$ to t , approximated as (small angle approx)

$$\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^e \approx \mathbf{C}_{b,t-1}^e (\mathbf{I}_3 + \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ib,t}^b \tau_i) - \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ie}^e \mathbf{C}_{b,t-1}^e \tau_i. \quad (1)$$

This attitude update matrix can be obtained in terms of the attitude increment. Taking into account that $m_{\alpha,t} > \gamma$ (to prevent division by zero, i.e., $m_{\alpha,t} > 1e-8$),

$$\mathbf{C}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{I}_3 + \frac{\sin(m_{\alpha,t})}{m_{\alpha,t}} \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ib,t}^b \tau_i + \frac{1 - \cos(m_{\alpha,t})}{m_{\alpha,t}^2} (\boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ib,t}^b \tau_i)^2,$$

otherwise we can use $\mathbf{C}_{t|t-1} = \mathbf{I}_3 + \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ib,t}^b \tau_i$. This can be used to obtain a more precise attitude update as

$$\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^e = \mathbf{C}_{Earth} \mathbf{C}_{b,t-1}^e \mathbf{C}_{t|t-1} \approx \mathbf{C}_{b,t-1}^e \mathbf{C}_{t|t-1} - \boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ie}^e \mathbf{C}_{b,t-1}^e \tau_i,$$

where

$$\mathbf{C}_{Earth} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\alpha_{ie}) & \sin(\alpha_{ie}) & 0 \\ -\sin(\alpha_{ie}) & \cos(\alpha_{ie}) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix},$$

To obtain the Euler angles, first the latitude (L_t) and longitude (λ_t) are obtained from the previous target's position (at $t-1$), $\mathbf{r}_{eb,t-1}^e$ (i.e., WGS84 geographical), then the coordinate transformation matrix is converted to the North-East-Down (NED) coordinate frame, $\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^n = \mathbf{C}_{e,t}^n \mathbf{C}_{b,t}^e$, using

$$\mathbf{C}_{e,t}^n = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin(L_t) \cos(\lambda_t) & -\sin(L_t) \sin(\lambda_t) & \cos(L_t) \\ -\sin(\lambda_t) & \cos(\lambda_t) & 0 \\ -\cos(L_t) \cos(\lambda_t) & -\cos(L_t) \sin(\lambda_t) & -\sin(L_t) \end{pmatrix}.$$

The Euler angles (roll, pitch, yaw) are computed as

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}_{b,t}^n(1) = \text{atan2}(\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^n(2, 3), \mathbf{C}_{b,t}^n(3, 3)), \quad (2)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}_{b,t}^n(2) = -\text{asin}(\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^n(1, 3)), \quad (3)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}_{b,t}^n(3) = \text{atan2}(\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^n(1, 2), \mathbf{C}_{b,t}^n(1, 1)). \quad (4)$$

¹Notation: $\mathbf{x}_{\beta\alpha}^\gamma \rightarrow \mathbf{x}$ of the α -frame axes with respect to the β -frame axes, resolved about the γ -frame axes, and a coordinate transformation matrix gives $\mathbf{x}_{\beta\alpha}^\delta = \mathbf{C}_{\gamma}^\delta \mathbf{x}_{\beta\alpha}^\gamma$.

- Velocity - $\mathbf{v}_{eb,t}^e$

The velocity is updated as

$$\mathbf{v}_{eb,t}^e = \mathbf{v}_{eb,t-1}^e + (\mathbf{f}_{ib,t}^e + \mathbf{g}_b^e(\mathbf{r}_{eb,t-1}^e) - 2\boldsymbol{\Omega}_{ie}\mathbf{v}_{eb,t-1}^e)\tau_i, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{g}_b^e(\mathbf{r}_{eb,t-1}^e)$ is the gravity vector with respect to the target position at $t - 1$. The accelerometer outputs (specific forces) transformed to the Earth-centered Earth-fixed (ECEF) frame of interest, can be approximated as $\mathbf{f}_{ib,t}^e \approx 1/2(\mathbf{C}_{b,t}^e + \mathbf{C}_{b,t-1}^e)\mathbf{f}_{ib,t}^b$ (average force between t and $t + \tau_i$).

- Position - $\mathbf{r}_{eb,t}^e$

The INS cartesian position is finally computed as,

$$\mathbf{r}_{eb,t}^e = \mathbf{r}_{eb,t-1}^e + \frac{(\mathbf{v}_{eb,t}^e + \mathbf{v}_{eb,t-1}^e)\tau_i}{2}. \quad (6)$$

As already stated, the main problem of low-cost standalone INS navigation is the impact of the sensor bias and noise. A constant rate-gyroscope bias error, when integrated, causes an angular error which grows linearly with time. A constant acceleration bias error, when double integrated, causes an error in position which grows quadratically with time. An illustrative simulated example is shown in Figure 1, where it is easy to see that the INS trajectory deviates from the true one and the error accumulates with time.

Fig. 1: Illustrative example of the impact of sensor bias into the INS solution (black line).

2.2. Loose GNSS/INS Fusion

In the loose GNSS/INS integration one have access to the following observations: GNSS position and velocity, $\mathbf{r}_{eaG,k}^e$ and $\mathbf{v}_{eaG,k}^e$; and INS acceleration (forces) and angular velocity, $\mathbf{f}_{ib,t}^b$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_{ib,t}^b$. Notice that the GNSS and INS measurement rates may be different. Both observations must be expressed in the same reference frame, so the INS solution must be converted from body to ECEF. To fuse both measurements, we have to define a state-space model (SSM), to apply an error-state KF. The state transition model is defined by the system, transition and system noise covariance matrices, $\mathbf{F}_{INS,t}$, $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_{INS,t}$ and $\mathbf{Q}_{INS,t}$, respectively; and the state to be estimated is $\mathbf{x}_{INS,t}$.

In an error-state fusion filter formulation, the main goal is to estimate the position and velocity errors at a given fusion rate t (this will be determined by the lower rate, which in general is given by the GNSS), $\delta\mathbf{r}_{eb,t}^e$ and $\delta\mathbf{v}_{eb,t}^e$, respectively. In addition we can add the attitude error, $\delta\boldsymbol{\psi}_{eb,t}^e$. We want to design a Kalman filter that estimates attitude, velocity and position errors, together with accelerometer and gyro biases, $\mathbf{b}_{a,t}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{g,t}$ (in total 15 states). The INS state (in ECEF coordinates) is given by

$$\mathbf{x}_{INS,t} = [\delta\boldsymbol{\psi}_{eb,t}^e; \delta\mathbf{v}_{eb,t}^e; \delta\mathbf{r}_{eb,t}^e; \mathbf{b}_{a,t}; \mathbf{b}_{g,t}]. \quad (7)$$

We consider the following notation:

- Raw inertial navigation solution: $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e, \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t}^e, \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e$
- Corrected inertial navigation solution: $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t}^e, \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e$
- Raw and corrected inertial solutions are related as: $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e = (\delta\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e)^\top \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t}^e = \tilde{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t}^e - \delta\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t}^e$ and $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e = \tilde{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e - \delta\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e$,
- In closed-loop architectures, there is no raw inertial solution, then: $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e = (\delta\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e)^\top \hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t-1}^e, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t}^e = \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t-1}^e - \delta\hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,t}^e$ and $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e = \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t-1}^e - \delta\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e$

Note that the state transition matrix Φ_{INS}^e is a power-series expansion (function of the system matrix \mathbf{F} and propagation interval τ_s). The KF design must determine which terms to include and which to neglect. The smaller the state propagation interval, τ_s , the smaller the higher-order terms will be. To ensure convergence, τ_s should be below 1 second. When there is a long interval between measurement updates, such as in many loosely coupled implementations, it may be necessary to run the system propagation at shorter intervals. The state or process equation is

$$\mathbf{x}_{\text{INS},t} = \Phi_{\text{INS}}^e \mathbf{x}_{\text{INS},t-1} + \mathbf{v}_{\text{INS},t}^e \quad (8)$$

with $\mathbf{v}_{\text{INS},t}^e \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_{\text{INS}}^e)$. The state transition matrix is approximated (first order in $\mathbf{F}\tau_s$) as

$$\Phi_{\text{INS}}^e \approx \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{I}_3 - \Omega_{ie}^e \tau_s & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e \tau_s \\ \mathbf{F}_{21}^e \tau_s & \mathbf{I}_3 - 2\Omega_{ie}^e \tau_s & \mathbf{F}_{23}^e \tau_s & \hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e \tau_s & \mathbf{0}_3 \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{I}_3 \tau_s & \mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{I}_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

where

$$\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e = (\delta\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e)^\top \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e \approx \left(\mathbf{I}_3 - [\delta\hat{\psi}_{eb,t}^e \wedge] \right) \tilde{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e, \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{21}^e = \left[- \left(\hat{\mathbf{C}}_{b,t}^e \hat{\mathbf{f}}_{ib,t}^e \right) \wedge \right], \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_{23}^e = - \frac{2\hat{\gamma}_{ib}^e}{r_{eS}^e(\hat{\mathbf{L}}_b)} \frac{(\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e)^\top}{|\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e|}, \quad (11)$$

with $[\mathbf{a} \wedge]$ representing a skew-symmetric matrix constructed from vector \mathbf{a} (more details in [1]), $r_{eS}^e(\hat{\mathbf{L}}_b)$ the geocentric radius at the Earth's surface as a function of the latitude, and $\hat{\gamma}_{ib}^e$ the gravitational acceleration at the estimated position $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,t}^e$. The system noise covariance matrix, $\mathbf{Q}_{\text{INS}}^e$, if we have small propagation intervals ($\tau_s < 0.2$ seconds), can be approximated by a block diagonal matrix

$$\mathbf{Q}_{\text{INS}}^e \approx \text{diag} (S_{rg} \mathbf{I}_3, S_{ra} \mathbf{I}_3, \mathbf{0}_3, S_{bad} \mathbf{I}_3, S_{bgd} \mathbf{I}_3) \tau_s, \quad (12)$$

with $S_{rg} = \sigma_{rg}^2 \tau_i, \sigma_{rg}^2$ the variance of the noise on the gyro angular-rate measurements, $S_{ra} = \sigma_{ra}^2 \tau_i, \sigma_{ra}^2$ the variance of the noise on the accelerometer specific-force measurements, τ_i the interval between the input of successive accelerometer and gyro outputs to the inertial navigation equations. The bias are statistically characterized by $S_{bad} = \sigma_{bad}^2 / \tau_{bad}$ and $S_{bgd} = \sigma_{bgd}^2 / \tau_{bgd}$, with σ_{bad}^2 and σ_{bgd}^2 the variances of the accelerometer and gyro dynamic biases, respectively; τ_{bad} and τ_{bgd} are the correlation times of the dynamic accelerometer and gyro biases.

Typically we use measurements from the GNSS, which minus the prediction of the same measurements obtained from the INS are used to construct the measurement innovation vector, to be used within the error-state KF. That is, in the loosely coupled GNSS/INS, the measurement innovation is directly the difference between GNSS position and velocity, and INS position and velocity (at the same rate, which requires the IMU and GNSS to be synchronized to the same time base). The measurement equation is

$$\mathbf{z}_{G,k} = \mathbf{H}_G^e \mathbf{x}_{\text{INS},k} + \mathbf{n}_{G,k}^e, \text{ with } \mathbf{n}_{G,k}^e \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_G), \quad (13)$$

with $\mathbf{z}_{G,k} = [\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eaG,k}^e, \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eaG,k}^e]^\top$. The innovation vector is

$$\delta \mathbf{z}_{G,k} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eaG,k}^e - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,k}^e \\ \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eaG,k}^e - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,k}^e \end{pmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

and the measurement matrix can be approximated as

$$\mathbf{H}_G^e \approx \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & -\mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 \\ \mathbf{0}_3 & -\mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{0}_3 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

The measurement noise covariance $\mathbf{R}_G \in \mathbb{R}^2$ must be set according to the error covariance of the GNSS navigation solution. The standard loose GNSS/INS architecture is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Loose GNSS/INS fusion architecture

2.3. Hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS Fusion

In order to consider a hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS integration architecture, range measurements provided by the cooperative UWB nodes must be included in the previous loose GNSS/INS SSM. This is done via an extra observation into the innovation vector. We must take into account that:

- The number of UWB range measurements available depends on the number of anchors in view, then, both the innovation vector and measurement matrix dimensions are time-varying.
- To obtain the INS-based distances to the different anchor nodes, a prediction block is included, which needs the set of anchor nodes' positions.
- With respect to standard tight integration architectures, there is no need to estimate the system clock offset because UWB measurements are synchronised with the GNSS clock (i.e., as IMU measurements).

The state to be tracked is again (7), and the innovation vector in this case is

$$\delta \mathbf{z}_{UG,k}^e = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eaG,k}^e - \hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb,k}^e \\ \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eaG,k}^e - \hat{\mathbf{v}}_{eb,k}^e \\ \delta \mathbf{z}_{\rho U,t}^e \end{pmatrix}, \quad (16)$$

with $\delta \mathbf{z}_{\rho U, t}^e = (\tilde{\rho}_U^1 - \hat{\rho}_{uI}^1, \tilde{\rho}_U^2 - \hat{\rho}_{uI}^2, \dots, \tilde{\rho}_U^L - \hat{\rho}_{uI}^L)_t$. $\tilde{\rho}_U^j$ are the UWB range measurements to L anchors ($j = 1, \dots, L$), and $\hat{\rho}_{uI}^j$, the corresponding INS-based prediction, which are obtained from both the INS position, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_{eb, t}^e$, and known anchors' positions, $\hat{\mathbf{r}}_U^j$. The measurement matrix is,

$$\mathbf{H}_{UG, t}^e = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{m,3} & \mathbf{0}_{m,3} & -\mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0}_{m,3} & \mathbf{0}_{m,3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{m,3} & -\mathbf{I}_3 & \mathbf{0}_{m,3} & \mathbf{0}_{m,3} & \mathbf{0}_{m,3} \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{\rho U}}{\partial \delta \psi_{eb}^e} & \mathbf{0}_{L,3} & \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}_{\rho U}}{\partial \delta \mathbf{r}_{eb}^e} & \mathbf{0}_{L,3} & \mathbf{0}_{L,3} \end{pmatrix}_{\mathbf{x}_t = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_t | t-1}$$

and $\mathbf{R}_{UG} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{R}_G, \mathbf{R}_{UWB})$.

Fig. 3: Hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS fusion architecture

3. PROTOTYPE

The multi-sensor data fusion prototype (shown in Figure 4) is based on:

- CPU module implemented using a Raspberry PI 3 model B board, which provides the necessary computing power for the multi-sensor data fusion algorithm.
- NAVIO2 IMU board (Emlid Ltd), which contains 2 low-cost IMUs with a 3-axis accelerometer, 3-axis gyroscope and 3-axis magnetometer
- A GNSS receiver (model UBLOX NEO-M8M), which provides measurements at 1 Hz. The GNSS is used to provide precise time-stamping to the other sensor measurements (IMU and UWB).
- The prototype can be powered with 8-16 V DC battery thanks to the embedded power supply voltage regulator.
- The inset software environment includes a Linux Raspbian operating system running a RT Linux Kernel provided by the IMU board manufacturer.
- Module Development and Evaluation Kit for the Decawave DWM1001 (MDEK1001) based on a UWB/Bluetooth module using Decawave's DW1000 RF transceiver and nRF52832 MCU running the Apache Mynewt real-time operating system flashed with Decawave's open-source firmware for two way ranging.

The firmware that implements the UWB ranging logic is, as of today, being under development in an effort to create an easy-to-use driver model that works with the Apache Mynewt embedded real-time operating system. Such firmware is an open-source initiative and is going through constant changes. For instance, a few issues that caused a disruption of the UWB network stability were discovered by the authors of the present work. These were reported to the firmware maintainers who released a patch that fixed some of the flaws. The firmware code is available in a public online repository and it should not be confused with Decawave’s closed-source firmware available on their website, which is based on FreeRTOS.

The open-source firmware that was used in this work is comprised by a stack of different software components which are found in separate online repositories. Namely, mynewt-dw1000-apps [6], the distribution containing example applications of real-time location systems; mynewt-dw1000-core [7], the device driver model for the Decawave DW1000 transceiver; mynewt-timescale-lib [8], a precompiled library for timescale processing that estimates clock skew and drift; apache-mynewt-core [9], the open-source real-time operating system for IoT devices; apache-mynewt-nimble [10], an open-source Bluetooth 5.0 stack; and mcuboot [11], an operating system and hardware independent secure bootloader for 32-bit microcontrollers.

Fig. 4: Navigation prototype

Fig. 5: Home built drone and hybrid navigation prototype

4. RESULTS

4.1. Case 1: Preliminary Indoor Drone Test

A first real measurement campaign with a preliminary UAV prototype was conducted at the CTTC premises to validate the proposed architecture, the real data setup and to assess the indoor positioning capabilities with respect to the ground truth obtained from a RCbenchmark Otus tracker. The first step was to locate the indoor UWB anchor nodes in the ECEF global frame to allow a later correct fusion with GNSS. Two GNSS reference stations were used to obtain the precise coordinates of two anchors outdoors and one reference point inside the building. The latter was used to obtain the remaining indoor anchor nodes' positions. Table 1 provides the coordinates of the anchor nodes in LLA format (altitude expressed above sea level), and a plot with their relative positions within the CTTC building is shown in (left plot) Figure 6.

Point Identifier	Latitude (deg)	Longitude (deg)	Altitude (m)
Node 1 (outdoor)	41° 16' 29.23"N	1° 59' 16.70"E	51.4016
Node 2 (outdoor)	41° 16' 29.18"N	1° 59' 16.37"E	51.3729
Node 3	41° 16' 29.32"N	1° 59' 16.33"E	54.4134
Node 4	41° 16' 29.40"N	1° 59' 16.64"E	54.2444
Node 5	41° 16' 29.48"N	1° 59' 16.26"E	54.4104
Node 7	41° 16' 29.39"N	1° 59' 16.30"E	55.5424
Node 8	41° 16' 29.49"N	1° 59' 16.62"E	55.5584
Node 9	41° 16' 29.68"N	1° 59' 16.36"E	54.5674
Node 10	41° 16' 29.27"N	1° 59' 16.47"E	54.3434

Table 1: Anchor nodes coordinates.

Fig. 6: Location of UWB anchors nodes (left). UAV indoor positioning using the hybrid solution with UWB distances for an indoor environment (right).

A test was performed inside the CTTC building with the preliminary prototype, running the hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS (HLC-UWB) fusion algorithm. A plot with both estimated and true trajectory are shown in (right plot) Figure 6, where only INS and UWB are used because the scenario is in GNSS-denied conditions. These results clearly validate the architecture and the INS/UWB fusion. Notice that the trajectory is not a real drone flight, which was moved following a drone-like flight but without engines, that is, without vibrations. We will see in the sequel that the latter is one of the main problems of the hybrid solution if using very low-cost sensors.

Fig. 7: Outdoor measurement campaign. GNSS track in green and UWB anchor nodes' position in pink. A view of the area on the right.

4.2. Case 2: Outdoor Drone Test

To validate the complete data fusion strategy (including GNSS position/velocity, UWB ranging and INS), a second measurement campaign was performed outdoors. It is shown in (right picture) Figure 7 that it is a clear-sky scenario, so not inducing any problems to GNSS positioning. In the left plot of the same Figure 7 we can see a set of real drone passes across the set of UWB anchor nodes (pink squares in the figure). Notice that in purpose the drone is entering and exiting the UWB visibility zone. The latter is used to have a realistic scenario, where a drone may be going sequentially from a safety-critical zone (equipped with UWB infrastructure) to unconstrained zones with GNSS only, and viceversa. To obtain a GNSS-denied environment to test the indoor/outdoor capabilities, in the results we emulate a GNSS tunnel (signal blocking) in postprocessing.

The results obtained for one of the passes are shown in Figure 8. The first plot (a) shows the comparison of the GNSS track in green, used as ground truth, and the standard loose GNSS/INS solution. It is clear that using a sensor fusion strategy in a drone is much more challenging than in more stable platforms such as cars, bicycles or pedestrians, mainly due to fast attitude changes and platform vibration. In this case, the system is able to correctly track the drone trajectory but with a positioning error larger than expected. We will discuss later which are the main reasons.

The second plot Figure 8 (b) shows the impact of an emulated tunnel into the standard loose GNSS/INS fusion, where during the GNSS signal blockage the system is performing INS standalone navigation. In this case, due to the poor quality of the IMU and the platform vibrations, blocking the GNSS signal induces an error of 40 meters (red line). Such error is corrected when including UWB-based ranging in the hybrid solution. This is shown in the bottom plots Figures 8 (c) and (d), where the hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS solution is compared with (d) and without (c) emulated tunnel. Comparing Figures 8 (b) and (d), that is, GNSS/INS and GNSS/UWB/INS with a tunnel, the performance improvement given by the new hybrid fusion architecture is more than justified. Then we can conclude that this is a promising solution for seamless indoor/outdoor navigation or in specific safety-critical applications where the UWB-based ranging infrastructure could be deployed.

Even if the results provided validate the proposed architecture, there are still some performance limitations which need to be improved, because the positioning error is not on the order of decimeters, which is what we would expect from the UWB-based navigation solution. There are three main reasons: i) poor quality of the inertial sensors used in the prototype, ii) vibration induced by the drone, and iii) a non-negligible impact of a small mismatch on the true anchors nodes' position. The second point is clear from Figure 9, where we show the raw accelerometer measurements (three phases: stopped, motors ON and flying), and we can identify the impact of the drone vibration, mainly in the z axis.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this contribution we proposed a hybrid solution fusing position and velocity provided by a Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) receiver, Ultra-WideBand (UWB)-based range measurements and an inertial navigation system (INS). The

Fig. 8: Results obtained with the different fusion strategies for the real outdoors drone flight.

data fusion is done via a Kalman filter (KF)-type algorithm (error-state KF) where the possibly time-varying number of visible UWB anchor nodes is taken into account. The proposed architecture has been implemented in a prototype, and results for real scenarios have been provided. Even if this contribution does not show an indoor/outdoor experiment, the system capabilities have been assessed via postprocessing of the real data, both indoors (standalone INS/UWB fusion) and with an emulated GNSS signal blocking. These results show the promising performance improvement of such approach with respect to standard GNSS/INS solutions. Considering that the corresponding UWB infrastructure can be deployed, the hybrid GNSS/UWB/INS presented in this article is not only a powerful solution for autonomous drone navigation in warehouses, factories or smart cities, but also for driverless cars and vulnerable road users (pedestrians, bicycles). Future work goes towards mitigation of the impact on the inertial sensors induced by the platform vibrations, and considering a possible model mismatch in the anchors' position.

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